

System design and economic benefits of controlled traffic farming in grass silage production

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Abstract

This paper reports on the range of commercially available equipment to configure grassland CTF systems with operating widths from 1.5m to 12m giving trafficked areas ranging from 40% to 13% respectively. The results of an economics analysis for four different guidance systems provides data on the additional cost per ha of the operation and compares this to the grass yield benefits from CTF systems, from which the breakeven areas are calculated. For areas larger than break-even, controlled traffic for a multi-cut grass silage system, is cost-effective in increasing yields due to a reduction in the extent of soil compaction and sward damage. UK£:US\$ rate £1.00 = \$1.25.

Background

The aim of this paper is to: (i) identify ranges of commercial grass forage equipment that could form the basis of controlled traffic systems (CTF) to reduce the extent of soil compaction and sward damage in grass production and (ii) conduct a cost/benefit analysis to determine the break-even values for a range of vehicle guidance systems. Following an extensive literature review (Hargreaves et al., 2016) and field studies in Scotland (Hargreaves et al., 2017), a number of viable CTF management systems based upon commercially available equipment ranging in widths from 3m to 12m were designed and an economics analysis conducted.

Methods

A wide range of commercial equipment was assessed to determine their basis for different widths of CTF system within grass silage production. The aim for each system was to select a combination of machinery that could be used with little or no physical modification or impact on field operations. Additionally, the machines were assessed for their compatibility with potential arable (combinable crop) operations on the same farm. The economics analysis follows a similar format to that used by Godwin et al. (2003), when assessing the potential for precision farming in cereal production. It considers the direct economic advantages from any improvements in forage yield alongside the costs of 4 alternative systems for vehicle guidance and steering. This considers the area of the grass farmed and estimates the breakeven crop area.

Results

CTF systems ranging from widths of 3 m to 12 m are feasible (Hargreaves et al., 2016), with trafficked areas ranging from 40% to 13%. When arable operations were introduced, the trafficked areas ranged from 58% to 18%. A wide range of options were possible, with the 5, 9 and 12 m systems leading to the lowest trafficked areas for both grassland and arable operations (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of the different CTF systems proposed and their associated trafficked areas

Controlled traffic base widths			Trafficked area, %	
Mowing width (m)	Other widths (m)	Forage system	Grass only	Grass & arable
1.5 or 3.0	6.0 & 9.0	Loader wagon	35.9	48.4
				57.8 (6 m combine)
				49.7 (9 m combine)
		Trailed forager	34.3	57.8 (6 m combine)
3.0	6.0 & 9.0	Self-propelled	40.1	44.1
				64.4 (6 m combine)
				44.1 (9 m combine)
4.0	8.0	Loader wagon	27.7	35.7 (4 m combine)
				40.5 (8 m combine)
				37.0 (8 m combine) ¹
5.0		Loader wagon	21.5	31.1
9.0		Self-propelled	18.2	22.0
12.0		Self-propelled	13.4	18.2

¹Combine harvester on rubber tracks

There are two shortcomings with the 4 and 5 m systems: a) loader wagon is required and b) the mower involved has heavily loaded wheels running on the non-trafficked bed. A 3 m system involves machines with little or no modification but requires a tractor with a track gauge of 1.5 m and because of its narrower width, has a greater tracked area than the wider systems. A 9 m system is achievable based on mowers such as shown in Figure 1, along with standard tedders, swathers, forage harvester and dribble bar slurry applicator. Harvesting with this 9 m system relies on delivery from a self-propelled harvester; either to rear hitched trailers that are swapped on the headland when full or to a specialist trailer on the adjacent traffic lane. There is presently no option for delivering to a trailer running in the adjacent traffic lane 9 m away. A further reduction in trafficked area could be achieved if the gauge of the harvester and other machinery in the operation were more closely aligned (Table 2). Introducing arable operations to this system does not increase the tracked area overly, with a predicted 22% being achieved (Table 1). The greatest constraint when introducing a CTF system is its effect on harvesting work rate, where the shortest route to the field exit is no longer permitted.

Figure 1. Triple gang mower of the type envisaged for a 9 m controlled traffic system and illustration of the machines and operations involved, including slurry spreading

Table 2. Machinery assumed for a 9 m controlled traffic system

Machine	Working width (m)	Operating width (m)	Tyres on principal axle ¹	Track gauge (m)
Claas Axion tractor	n/a	n/a	710/70 R 38	2.0
Kuhn GMD 9530 triple gang mower	9.13-9.53	9.0		
Claas Volto tedder	10.7	9.0		
Kuhn GA 9531 swather	8.4-9.30	9.0		
Claas Jaguar 980/940 harvester		9.0	710/70 R 42	2.20
Richard Western silage trailer	n/a	9.0	15x22.5 – 18 PR	2.0
Conor slurry tanker + trailing shoe	9	9.0	560/60 R 22.5	2.04
Agrisem Vibromulch stubble cultivator	9	9.0		
Dale Eco-Drill	9	9.0		
John Deere 9000 series combine	9.14	9.0	650/75 R 32	2.61
Grain chaser	2.91	9.0	800/40 R 26.5	2.11

¹Tyres on the axle that creates the widest footprint for the particular machine.

A range of trafficked areas (%) was used in the economics analysis, as these depend upon the operating track gauges and wheel widths of the available equipment, thus enabling the farmer to estimate the benefits for their system. The cost of CTF is based upon four different levels of capital investment, as the level of expenditure will depend upon the type and scale of the operation.

The additional costs are focused on the costs of the guidance systems only, as it is assumed that initially a farmer or contractor would use existing equipment and that improvements to equipment matching would be part of the normal longer-term replacement policy. In practice multiple guidance systems may be required to support the harvester and other operations. Hence, the costs of each individual guidance system are estimated, from which the costs of multiple systems are considered.

Douglas et al. (1992 and 1995) and Frost (1988a and 1988b) indicated that the removal of wheel traffic increased the average grass yield by 14.7% and 12.1% respectively. Hence for the purpose of this study a mean potential yield increase of 13% was selected which was similar to the results of the parallel field study reported by Hargreaves et al., (2017). The actual yield benefit for a range of reduced trafficked areas from an assumed maximum of 45% to a minimum of 15% was calculated and shown in Table 1. These data were calculated by assuming:

1. The average forage dry matter yield for 2 and 3 cut systems per year in the UK is 12 t ha⁻¹ and 16.5 t ha⁻¹ (mean of the range 15 – 18 t ha⁻¹) respectively (SRUC, 2016).
2. The fields are currently managed with non-controlled traffic patterns covering 80% of the field.

The figure of 80% was chosen given the recorded data of the trafficked area for a single harvest operation of 65% from Kroulík et al., (2014) and that during a growing season where there could be in excess of 11 multiple operations. It is higher than the 74% chosen by Alvemar (2014) but more conservative than assuming a total (100%) trafficked area. These assumptions result in calculated yield increases from 0.53t ha⁻¹ to 0.99t ha⁻¹ and 0.73t ha⁻¹ to 1.36t ha⁻¹ for 2 and 3 cut/season systems respectively, as given in Table 3 by adding the trafficked and non - trafficked yields.

Table 3. Estimated yield and yield increase as affected by reductions in the trafficked area (%) for 2 and 3 cut/season systems

Trafficked Area, %	2 Cut/season 80% = 12.0 t ha ⁻¹		3 Cut/season 80%=16.5 t ha ⁻¹	
	Yield, t ha ⁻¹	Yield increase, t ha ⁻¹	Yield, t ha ⁻¹	Yield increase, t ha ⁻¹
45	12.53	0.53	17.23	0.73
35	12.68	0.68	17.44	0.94
25	12.83	0.83	17.65	1.15
15	12.99	0.99	17.86	1.36

Figure 2 shows the yield increases in economic terms assuming that the crop has a value of £72 (\$90) t⁻¹ of dry matter giving benefits of £38 (\$47) ha⁻¹ to £71 (\$89) ha⁻¹ and £ 53 (\$66) ha⁻¹ to £98 (\$123) ha⁻¹ for the 2 and 3 cut systems respectively. This equates to £1.10 (\$1.38) ha and £1.50 (\$1.90) ha for every 1% reduction in trafficked area for the 2 and 3 cut systems. These economic benefits are broadly in agreement with Alvemar (2014) in Sweden at £40 (\$50) ha⁻¹ to £49 (\$61) ha⁻¹ and Stewart et al. (1998) in Scotland at £79 (\$99) ha⁻¹.

Figure 2. The effect of reducing the trafficked area (%) on the potential economic benefit.
Dash line - 2 Cuts/season (12 t ha⁻¹); Solid line - 3 Cuts/season (16.5 t ha⁻¹)

Typical costs of alternative machine guidance systems are given in Table 4. They include the capital expenditure for the receivers and subscription fees, at four levels of investment. These range from elementary systems using a light bar and manual steering with a low level of accuracy, to assisted steering with both low and higher accuracy and fully integrated steering systems with high accuracy levels. To provide both improved accuracy and repeatable positioning real time kinematic (RTK) navigation systems are required, therefore adding the cost of a network subscription fee. This was chosen as an alternative to factoring in the additional capital costs of a base station. It should be noted that the lower accuracy systems could result in higher trafficked areas.

Table 4. Current typical commercial equipment guidance costs/system

Investment	Equipment	Repeatable positioning	Capital Cost	RTK Annual Fee	Total Annual Cost†
Level 1	Low accuracy*	No	£1,500	-	£468
	Manual steering		(\$1875)		(\$585)
Level 2	Low accuracy*	No	£5,000	-	£1325
	Assisted steering		(\$6250)		(\$1656)
Level 3	High accuracy**	Yes	£10,000	£500	£3050
	Assisted Steering		(\$12500)	(\$625)	(\$3813)
Level 4	High accuracy**	Yes	£15,000	£500	£4275
	Integrated steering		(\$18750)	(\$625)	(\$5344)

***(+/-150 - 200mm) These may result in an increase in trafficked area due to their lower accuracy and non-repeatable positioning. **(+/-20mm) Real Time Kinematic (RTK)**

†The total annual cost includes interest rates (4.5%), depreciation - 5years with a residual value of 25% (15% year-1), maintenance (5%) and training (£100 (\$125)/year) (Nix, 2015).

The annual cost/ha for the four system levels are given in Figure 3 for a range of areas. The figure of 1500 ha is the assumed upper limit for a given harvester and associated guidance equipment during a single cutting period. This is based upon typical harvesting rates of 75 ha day-1 (Farmers Weekly 25/3/2016 and 1/4/2016) and an assumed minimum 20workdays/cutting period for a contractor-based system. The data in Figure 3 show the dramatic effect that the size of the area harvested has on the cost/ha, with the costs/ha becoming asymptotic to the horizontal axis. This shows that the £1,500 (\$1875) system costs less than £4.68 (\$5.85) ha-1 for areas in excess of 100 ha with the more expensive £15,000 (\$18750) system, costing £21.38 (\$26.73) ha-1 for areas in excess of 200 ha reducing to £2.85 (\$3.53) ha-1 for areas in excess of 1500 ha.

Figure 3. Annual cost/ha/system of the guidance system for four levels of capital expenditure.

Dotted line - £1500 (\$1875); Dash-dot line – £5000 (\$6250); Dash line – £10,000 (\$12500); Solid line – £15,000 (\$18750).

Discussion

With CTF systems in grassland it is not only the harvester that needs to be equipped with machine guidance systems but also the tractors drawing trailers and other field operations. The data in Figure 3 enables the reader to determine the total cost for the number of systems required for their operation and to maybe have different levels of technology for the harvester and tractor based operations for a given harvested area. For example, using the data in Fig 3 shows that 4 off £1,500 (\$1875) systems costs less than £18.70 (\$23.38) ha⁻¹ for areas in excess of 100 ha and 4 off £15,000 (\$18750) systems, cost £85.50 (\$107) ha⁻¹ for areas in excess of 200 ha reducing to £11.40 (\$14.25) ha⁻¹ for areas in excess of 1500 ha. By comparing the costs (Figure 3) and potential benefits (Figure 2) that is (Total annual cost (£)/Annual economic benefit (£ ha⁻¹)) the break even areas can be calculated. The break-even area for 4 off £15,000 (\$18750) guidance systems is 450 ha for 2 cuts/season with a 45% trafficked area and 50 ha for 4 off £1,500 (\$1875) guidance systems. For a 15% trafficked area with 3 cuts/season these reduce to 172 ha and 19 ha for the Level 4 and Level 1 systems respectively.

It is also possible to undertake an analysis of individual operations, for example: a farm with 200 ha of grass with 3 cuts/season, where CTF can reduce the trafficked area from 80% to 40% is contemplating the purchase of a £10,000 (\$12500) navigation system for the harvester and two £5,000 (\$6250) systems for the supporting tractors.

- a. Figure 2 shows a benefit of £60 (\$75) ha⁻¹ for the 3 cut system with a 40% trafficked area.
- b. Figure 3 shows for an area of 200 ha the cost of the £10,000 (\$12500) navigation system is £15.25 (\$19) ha⁻¹ and £6.63 (\$8.29) ha⁻¹ for each of the £5,000 systems, giving a total of £28.50 (\$36.63) ha⁻¹.
- c. The break-even area is the total annual cost (from Table 4) = £3050 + (2 x £1325) = £5700 (\$7125) divided by the benefit of £60 (\$75) ha⁻¹, giving 95 ha.
- d. The net benefit of conversion to CTF with a trafficked area of 40% gives rise to £60 (\$75) ha⁻¹ less £28.50 (\$35.63) ha⁻¹ = £31.50 (\$39.37) ha⁻¹. This equates to £6300 (\$7875) for the farm.

Conclusions

1. CTF systems can be configured to operate with mowing widths from 1.5 to 12m giving trafficked areas from 36 to 13% respectively. They can be integrated with arable crops in the rotation.
2. Providing the navigation systems are wisely selected for the size of the operation then controlled traffic farming in grassland can be cost effective. The data given are aimed at allowing the benefits, costs and break-even areas of individual systems to be estimated and investment choices to be made.

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